

Bologna Living Lab. Pilot project for implementation of serious game in citizen science initiatives

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Abstract

Nowadays, climate change shows irreversible consequences for the well-being of humanity, territories, and resources. The city of Bologna (Italy) is facing environmental, societal, and digital challenges that are currently featured in urban spaces worldwide: air pollution and intense urban mobility, due to anthropic activities and ever-increasing urbanization. A just socio-ecological transition towards sustainable urban spaces relies on the collaboration among all actors involved in the Quintuple Helix of Innovation (Carayannis et al, 2012). In an attempt to address these challenges, researchers from the University of Bologna established the Bologna Living Lab, actively engaging a comprehensive network of stakeholders including policy and decision-makers, academic and research institutions, civil society, and industry aiming to democratize knowledge and research in the environmental field. The H2020 I-CHANGE project "Individual Change of HAbits Needed for Green European transition" intends to demonstrate how collective behavioral change is possible through the involvement of civil society in citizen science initiatives (Goudeseune et al, 2020; Vohland, 2021). The research approach is structured around Living Labs (LLs) to raise awareness about climate change impacts in urban space and to promote behavioral changes toward more socially and environmentally sustainable lifestyles.

Key words

Citizen science, urban mobility, air pollution, serious game, just transition, behavioral change, STS, co-creation

Raising climate awareness and promoting more sustainable lifestyle in urban space

Introduction

The city of Bologna (Italy) is facing environmental, societal, and digital challenges that are currently featured in urban spaces worldwide: air pollution and intense urban mobility, due to anthropic activities and ever-increasing urbanization. In an attempt to address these challenges, researchers from the University of Bologna established the Bologna Living Lab, a democratic science space where researchers and members of civil society collaborate in the definition of environmental protection and climate actions to undermine inequality in the eco-social just transition framework.

Bologna Living Lab is implemented within the H2020 I-CHANGE project "Individual Change of HABits Needed for Green European transition". It intends to demonstrate how collective behavioral change is possible through the involvement of civil society in citizen science initiatives (Goudeseune et al, 2020; Vohland, 2021) in the setting of Living Labs. The project has built a wide network of Living Labs, operating at a local level and cooperating at an international scale, since they set up in six cities in Europe (Amsterdam, Barcelona, Bologna, Dublin, Genoa, Hasselt), two in extra-European countries, one in West Asia (Jerusalem) and one in West Africa (Ouagadougou). The project started in November 2021, and it will end in April 2025.

Methodology

In Bologna, the Living Lab is actively engaging a comprehensive network of stakeholders including policy and decision-makers, academic and research institutions, civil society, and industry. Bologna Living Lab stakeholders have been mapped thoroughly in the framework of the Quintuple Helix (Carayannis et al, 2012) with a Multilevel perspective (Geels, 2011). To identify the needs and the specific role of each stakeholder, the research team delivered a survey to classify and assign the proper role in the project according to their relevance level (De Vincente Lopez & Matti, 2016, p. 46-53). Four main roles have been identified in the project for stakeholders: enabler, user, provider, and consumer (Leminen et al, 2014). Each role requires a different level of engagement and different activities to be involved in. For example, students involved will represent providers for data collection via maps and surveys; social scientists and atmospheric physicists will enable the data elaboration. The results produced will intertwine with the activities of the Municipality of Bologna (provider of information

and data) and with initiatives of local Associations, users of the innovative results developed by the Living Lab.

According to one of I-CHANGE's purposes, the social scientist operating in Bologna Living Lab developed a social and economic tool for the analysis and evaluation of behavioral changes. The main activities implemented in the Bologna LL were carried out in two macro directions: on the one hand, the dissemination of a survey to understand the level of climate awareness and the factors capable of directing a change in behavior, and on the other hand, the experience of a serious game on urban mobility practices. These activities are to be considered interrelated, as useful steps to analyze and understand the areas of possible intervention, identifying guidelines and recommendations to be shared with local institutions dealing with urban policies.

As a first step, a semi-structured survey grid has been created and addressed to target groups (students, citizens, consumers) selected with a snowball sampling methodology (Parker et al, 2019). Data collection and analysis has been guided by COM-B model (Fig.1), a theoretical framework based on Theory of Change (Mayne, 2015; Stein & Valters, 2015) to set goals and outcome for understanding and supporting a concrete and effective behavior change (Keyworth et al, 2020; Michie et al, 2013). The grid is designed to investigate 6 dimensions that could drive behavioral decisions, namely physical capability, psychological capability, physical opportunity (afforded by the environment, including time and resources), social opportunity (afforded by interpersonal influences, social cues), reflective motivation and automatic motivation. The evaluation tools consider not only behavioral changes that have occurred, *process indicators*, but also their socio-economic durability and sustainability over time, *impact indicators* (Gertler, 2011; Håk et al, 2012).

Figure 1. COM-B Model (Michie et al. 2011)

The three dimensions of COM-B were retraced to structure the areas to investigate to identify, according to the respondents, what are the factors most likely to impact a behavioral change. In our case, it was not necessary to delve into what the concrete interventions to be implemented might be. Indeed, we used the COM-B model to explore some aspects and/or characteristics to take into consideration when assessing and evaluating outcomes and impacts of citizen science activities.

Based on the collective answer, the survey helped identify what individual, collective, or structural clinchers can contribute to supporting concrete and effective change toward more sustainable lifestyles. We specified how there were no right or wrong answers, and participants were invited to respond according to their own views on the topic.

The survey is structured into four main sections:

- a. *climate change awareness*, to assess the level of understanding of the issue;
- b. section identifying factors influencing behavior change in actions areas related to urban mobility and air pollution (Tab.1). Questions are related to *capabilities* and *opportunities* that can foster or hinder behavior change (Tamlin et al, 2020);
- c. section on *motivation* (Tab.2), to explore the extent to which certain factors may promote or limit participation in a project on climate change and environmental issues and their impacts. Questions were built on the outcomes of the literature review (Abernathy et al, 2022)
- d. *socio-demographic section*

Table 1. *Capabilities and Opportunities Indicators of behavioral change. Left column, researchers' agreed vocabulary; right column, extended sentences on the survey. XXX has been replaced with the Action Area in each survey. (I-CHANGE D1.4, 2022)*

Capabilities	
Knowledge and skills	
Knowledge	To what extent would more information about XXX influence a person's decision to use them?
Beliefs	How much would the environmental impact of a type of XXX affect a decision to adopt it?
Skills	How much would the expertise on XXX affect a decision to adopt it?
Education	How much would the education you receive (school, peers, family) about XXX affect your decision to put in place actions to mitigate their impacts?
Experience and habits	

Experience	Does previous experience of XXX increase the willingness to use it?
Cultural norms	Does the general behavior and habits of someone's cultural context support a sustainable XXX choice?
Social Status	How much does someone's social status (e.g., social or/and economic position in society) affect the choice of XXX?
Gender	How much does someone's gender affect their choice of using XXX?
Biology and health	
Type and degree of existing health	How much would health condition impact the choice of XXX?
Cognitive, mental, or physical disability	How much would a cognitive, mental or physical disability impact the choice to put in place actions to mitigate XXX?
Chronic illness	How much would chronic illness impact the choice to put in place actions to mitigate XXX?
Opportunities	
Support and services	
Availability and continuity of social support and ties	How much does family/social network support influence someone's decision to XXX?
Availability of appropriate services	Would a good sustainable transport infrastructure increase the use of XXX?
Availability of appropriate resources	Do you think that more resources (economic, access to knowledge to individual impacts on air pollution) affect the choice to put in place actions to mitigate XXX?
Access, barriers, and opportunities	
Physical access	How much does physical accessibility affect the use of XXX?
Communication	How much does comprehensible communication affect the choice to put in place actions to mitigate XXX?
Discrimination	How much does age, race, gender, sex, ability discrimination affect the choice to put in place actions to mitigate XXX?
Consequences of efforts	
Social approval or disapproval	How much does social, cultural, and common approval on tools and infrastructure to mitigate impacts of XXX affect its use?
Incentives and disincentives	How much do incentives on tools and infrastructure to mitigate impacts of XXX affect your everyday life to prevent it?
Time costs	How much does travel time affect the use of XXX?
Policies and living conditions	
Policies	How much do government policies on XXX affect its adoption?
Financial barriers	How much does the ticket price affect the use of XXX / How much does the cost of tools and infrastructure to mitigate impacts of XXX affect their adoption?
Exposure to hazards	How much does personal safety impact someone's decision to use XXX?

Living conditions	How much does lifestyle (job, children, need of multiple rides during the day etc.) influence someone's decision to use XXX?
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Table 2. Motivation Indicators to join a project related to climate change. Left column, researchers' agreed vocabulary; right column, extended sentences on the survey. (I-CHANGE D1.4, 2022)

MOTIVATION	
Appreciation	Possible feeling of being appreciated
Accomplishment	Possible feeling of being accomplished
Acknowledgment	Knowing that I could be acknowledged of my commitment
Clear Goals	Clear project goals
Clear Timeline	Clear guidelines and timeline
Collective aim	The aims of the project at individual and collective level
Communication	Accessible and clear communication
Group	Possibility to join a group
Impact	Knowing that the project would have concrete impacts
Open Data	Knowing that data produced will be accessible and open
Role	Having a specific role in the project

In the first batch of the selected sample between June and July 2022, a selective mechanism in the Climate Change awareness evaluation allows a distinction between people who think their behavior has a low impact on climate change issues and the ones who believe they can have an impact. The first type of people skipped the whole topic insight section and jumped directly to the motivation to join a project on climate change. This differentiation allowed the researchers to pin a focus point not only on how to change the behavior of citizens but also on the importance of raising awareness before any citizen science activity.

A second questionnaire's structure has been piloted in April 2023 with a selective question on participation in citizen science projects. The goal is to be able to administer the survey to a selected group of citizens who attend Living Lab activities to investigate in depth how much involvement in citizen science activities leads a person to change his or her habits toward more conscious and sustainable choices or if it does not result in any significant effect. The survey's results will be compared to a sample of citizens who were instead sure not to have participated in any activities.

The second research activity aimed to investigate how the adoption of sustainable mobility practices is closely linked to the different lifestyles of Bologna citizens, a Serious Game was tested with students of the Environmental Sociology course at the

University of Bologna in April 2023. The students, divided into groups, were given fictitious characters (personas) with targeted socio-demographic characteristics gathered from what the literature and the first survey identified as barriers for sustainable behavioral choices: gender, age, health status, family composition, work position, economic situation. Each personas features a mobility daily schedule (*Fig.1*) and quests to complete using the three main modes of urban transports, if applicable (private car, bicycle/foot, public transport) and different policy scenarios (30 areas, low emission areas), already or in progress to be implemented in the city of Bologna. Students then had to develop different mobility solutions on a paper map (*Fig.2*), also acquiring information from the tools provided by the Municipality of Bologna (PUMS, PGTU, maps) and the Emilia-Romagna Region. The results, still processing, aim to identify good practices or areas for improvement in the urban mobility system. The cartographic research work is enriched by quali-quantitative research (questionnaires and semi-structured interviews) and the elaboration of statistical models on urban traffic in collaboration with the Physics Department of the University of Bologna, to help students to describe as accurately as possible the complexity of the mobility system involving social, economic, and technological variables.

Gabriela - collaboratrice domestica			
Persona	35 - 45 anni Collaboratrice domestica in diverse case del Centro Città Due figli (6 e 10 anni). Orari: scuola 8.30 - 16.30		
Mobilità	Non ha la patente né della macchina né del motorino e di conseguenza non li possiede. In famiglia possiedono delle biciclette ma non è solita usarle. Ha l'abbonamento dell'autobus.		
Luoghi	Casa	Via Fornasini	
	Scuola dei figli	Primaria "Casaralta"	
	Lavoro A	Via Farini	
	Lavoro B	Via Manin	
	Spesa	ALDI, via della Liberazione	
Agenda	Mobility Agenda		
	Orario	Spostamenti	Mezzo
	< 7	Partenza da casa	
	7 - 8	Arrivo nel luogo di lavoro A	
	8 - 12		
12 - 13	Spostamento nel luogo di lavoro B		
13 - 14			
14 - 16			
16 - 17	Uscita dal lavoro, ritiro dei bambini da scuola		
17 - 18	Spesa		
18 - 19			
19 - 21 <	Ritorno a casa		

Figure 2. Example of Personas' mobility schedule (italian language)

Figure 3. Example of map elaboration from the student activity held in April 2023

In the coming months (summer and fall), after careful evaluation of the results of the pilot activity with students, the serious game will also be submitted to selected groups of stakeholders interested in sustainable mobility and air quality. Involving more stakeholders in the serious game and in filling out the questionnaire to expand the critical mass of data is intended to achieve two goals: on the one hand, deliver suggestions to municipalities and decision-makers based on solid science, and on the other hand, to contribute to social research on how to stimulate a change of life for a more sustainable future.

Conclusions

The goal of the research is to create a tool that enables the assessment of citizens' behavioral change before and after participating in citizen science activities in the Living Lab. To achieve this goal, the main tool used is the qualitative-quantitative questionnaire, assisted by focus groups, administered before and after the proposed activities to living lab participants. At present, the data processed is that of the first 200 questionnaires describing the current state of the population of Bologna, to which should be added those collected during the second phase of research that will end in May 2023, achieving the critical number of at least 500 surveys.

Initial results show that the average awareness of the impact on climate change in cities is low compared to the level of education of all respondents, contrary to the literature. In fact, out of the 79% of respondents with a higher education degree, only the 47% think that they could have a moderate or major impact on climate change.

Out of 11 “Motivation on joining a climate project”, 10 dimensions of data identified are consistent with the literature review carried on by Abertnathy et al (2022). On the other hand, “Group” dimension has been indicated as the least important motivation in clear contrast with literature, where the feeling to belong to a group is identified as a relevant driver for participation in environmental-related projects. Thirdly, gender appears to be the least important indicator for all respondents no matter their gender, age, or education level. This data is at odds with literature related to the eco-gender gap (Normandin, 2020). It could mean that among respondents the perception of the gender perspective is less relevant or underestimated than what is reported in the relevant literature. Gender is, in fact, a determinant variable with respect to both awareness about climate change and the possibility of adopting more sustainable and eco-friendly

behaviors (Simićević et al, 2016; Swim et al. 2018, 2020; Normandin, 2020). This opens a new field of research to investigate.

In May, the researchers will conclude the activity with students and administer the survey for the second time to find out if any differences appear after participating in a citizen science activity. In June and September 2023, the same Serious Game will be offered to key stakeholders of Bologna Living Lab relevant also at the policy and decision-making level. The expectation is to provide not only an evaluation tool for Living Labs to assess the effectiveness of involving citizens towards a sustainable lifestyle, but also to carry out consistent data useful for evidence-based decision making for local ecosystem where the Living Lab operates, becoming itself a key actor in climate action.

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